

At: Internacional Seminar: Public Health, Urban Planning, and Local Institutions – Health Policies and Social Inequalities in the Iberian Peninsula Throughout the 19th Century, organized by Lab2PT/IN2PAST and CIES-ISCTE-IUL, 28-29.05.2026, Braga, Portugal.

**The Hospital de Santo António
in times of epidemics:
vulnerability and resilience in
Porto of eight hundred (1850-
1900)**

1 Célia Oliveira - Lab2PT/IN2PAST, University of Minho, PT
2 FCT scholarship ref. 2023.05192.BD

BeFRAIL - Porto in Times of Cholera and War: A Bioarchaeological Approach to Human Frailty. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.54499/2022.02398.FTDC>.

Logos: Lab2PT, IN2PAST, BeFRAIL, CIAA, FCT, REPÚBLICA PORTUGUESA

Title: The Hospital de Santo António in times of epidemics: vulnerability and resilience in Porto of eight hundred (1850-1900)

Célia OLIVEIRA^{1,2}

1 Lab2PT – Laboratory of Landscapes, Heritage and Territory (University of Minho, Braga, Portugal)

2 IN2PAST – Associate Laboratory for Research and Innovation in Heritage, Arts, Sustainability and Territory (University of Évora, Portugal)

Abstract: During the nineteenth century, the city of Porto experienced a succession of crises that profoundly shaped the lives of its inhabitants. Armed conflicts, political instability, social tensions, and recurrent epidemic outbreaks created a climate of uncertainty and hardship, revealing and often exacerbating existing social inequalities. Within this context of widespread vulnerability, epidemic diseases posed some of the greatest challenges to both the population and local institutions, placing considerable pressure on healthcare systems and frequently prompting urgent action from public authorities.

As municipal and state authorities introduced sanitary regulations aimed at containing the spread of disease, hospitals assumed a central role in caring for the sick with the limited resources available to them. Founded in 1770 by the Santa Casa da Misericórdia

do Porto, Santo António Hospital emerged as the city's principal healthcare institution and one of its most significant centres of medical assistance.

This study investigates the hospital's response to epidemic emergencies by examining the strategies adopted to manage outbreaks, including administrative measures, institutional regulations, therapeutic resources, medical and nursing personnel, and hospital facilities. It also seeks to assess the institution's limitations and operational difficulties, while identifying patterns of adaptation, continuity, and resilience in the face of recurring health crises. The research is based on the combined analysis of secondary literature and archival documentation, with particular emphasis on the reports produced by the Santa Casa da Misericórdia do Porto.

Keywords: Epidemics; Human vulnerability; Healthcare institutions; Hospital resilience; Porto.